

DRIVERS INFLUENCE THE CUSTOMER'S WILLINGNESS TOWARDS FINANCIAL TECHNOLOGY FIRMS DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC – EVIDENCE FROM INDIA

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Abstract

The demonetization in the year 2016 in India, called the landmark moment for the financial technology (FinTech) firms to expand their wings and landscape, is one of the significant stimulating digital economic ecosystems eras in India. More than 21,000 FinTech companies and start-ups have made a drastic change in the indispensable part of people's lives during times of pandemics. The paper examines the drivers influencing customers' acceptance or willingness towards FinTech products and services that most studies remain unexplored. The study will review the factors like perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, users mindset, user behavior, trust, and security as the critical factor variables for accepting/rejecting the customer's decision in the direction of the fintech products and services. The data collection will be both primary and secondary methods. The survey data will be collected from google forms. A five-point Likert scale will be used to capture the responses. The descriptive and exploratory research designs are used for the study. Appropriate statistical tools such as Mean, standard deviation, multi-regression analysis, Conbranch alpha, t-test, f-test, Durban Watson test, etc., will be used. This paper will suggest the ongoing and future policy responses to the spread of the COVID-19. Ultimately, this study also gave a glow on the effects COVID-19 has on general wellbeing in the short term and points some potential areas that need extra support.

Keywords: Financial Technology (FinTech), customer's willingness, perceived usefulness, ease of use, COVID-19.

JEL Classification Code: G2, G4, G5

1. Introduction

The fintech marketplace has endured helping amplify entry to financial offerings at some point of the COVID-19 pandemic—specifically in rising markets—with a substantial boom in all forms of virtual financial offerings. Fintech improvements support the cost of supplying offerings, making it viable to reach extra humans, and decreasing the want for face-to-face interactions, vital for retaining up financial activity at some stage in the pandemic. According to FCDO (Foreign, Commonwealth & Development Office) -"Covid-19 is accelerating change in how people interact with financial services, which has led to unprecedented demand from developing countries to progress their transition to secure and inclusive digital finance."

With the development of Internet technology, there have been many disruptive innovations in the financial industry, and financial technology (FinTech) has become popular in mobile payment, lending, personalized investment, and so on (Anagnostopoulos, 2018).

India has secured the second position globally with the most distinguished fintech start-up (following the United States in 2018). Over three hundred start-up conditions existed between 2015 to 2018). Government initiative toward selling digitization of financial systems and cashless economic system has helped shift customers' recognition towards digital alternatives for monetary transactions and offerings. The adoption of Fintech global grew at 64% in 2019, and in rising markets, like China and India, the boom is at 87%.

Concurrently, the ongoing unfold of COVID-19 has come to be one of every of the most critical threats to the global economy and financial markets. The effect of the coronavirus outbreak, India, like many countries across the globe, is taking several measures, including a nationwide lockdown; limiting motion of the whole population; shutting down public locations and transport, and urging the general public to live indoors, keep social distance, and do business from home. The damaging results of the COVID-19 pandemic are losing down to essential sectors of the Indian economic system, with production, car, retail, aviation, and hospitality bearing the brunt of the lockdown. But, a few areas are seeing an uptick in virtual bills through accelerated adoption throughout the lockdown. Those encompass online grocery stores, online pharmacies, OTT players (telecom and media), online education, online gaming, recharge, software/invoice payments, etc. The COVID-19 pandemic has had a significant effect across sectors in India and disrupted enterprise operations. The FinTech sector is not any exception, and various segments within this region had been impacted. But, the quantity of the impact differs (Sudhakar Ramasubramanian Chair, FICCI Fintech Committee, and chief digital Officer, IndusInd bank 2020).

1.1 COVID 19 LOCKDOWN and FinTech: Overview

"The IMF sees GDP per capita shrinking across 170 nations due to the corona virus pandemic. The IMF noted that even a short-lived outbreak would drag the world into a 3% GDP contraction. A resurgence of COVID-19 in 2021 could leave economies struggling for years to come." – *I.M.F.* Digital bills-Unified Payments Interface (UPI), a real-time, immediate price gadget is facilitating inter-bank transactions, turned into advanced by using the national payments agency of India (NPCI) and allowed via the RBI to offer services. They're formalizing the FinTech area with the aid of putting in place widespread running procedures (SOPs), rules, compliances, and recommendations and selling innovation, transparency, inclusion, and access through initiatives. Technological development includes specific initiatives such as the improvement of IndiaStack, the arena's most significant proposed series of open software programming interfaces (APIs), and the provision of a low-fee net. rising technology is the spine of the whole FinTech surroundings and play a crucial role in revolutionizing the arena. FinTechs leverage advanced analytics and artificial intelligence (AI) for process automation, consumer engagement, fraud analytics etc.

Source: KPMG

Figure 1: Total Investment of Fintech in India.

One of the 'Gaint four' accounting businesses globally, despite the fact that massive disruptions in economic activities were discovered throughout the globe, India's fintech area acted immensely active inside the first six months of 2020. The fintech begin-U.S. in India obtained a hefty \$1,699.9 million investment in H1 2020 across 70 offers. That is greater than double the amount to the year in the past, wherein this space raised \$726.6 million.

1.2 Impact on the Indian economy

India has a total workforce of about 500 million, and a surprising ninety% of the personnel are within the casual quarter. Many contractual workers and each day salary earners across industries face employment uncertainties or have been out of work because the authorities imposed lockdown in March 2020. The worldwide economic Fund (IMF) has projected India's GDP increase inside the present-day fiscal year (FY20-21) at 1.9%. However, several different businesses have predicted even lower GDP growth costs. Source: thehindubusinessline.com 14th April 2020. Even fintech companies faced challenges due to the Covid-19 pandemic in various segments such as payments, alternative lending, wealth tech, Insutech, etc. In addition to, Impact on consumer behavior - Loss or reduction of income could affect consumption and expenditure patterns worldwide. Businesses could be affected by the absence or decrease in customers, low-income workers, and lack of fresh capital, pushing them to dip into their cash reserves for survival.

2. Review of Literature

Various research studies have been conducted worldwide on fintech digital products and services context, and TAM has been widely referred to inside the studies context in more than one setting (Muk & Chung, 2015; Tarhini, Hassouna, Abbasi, & Orozco, 2015). concerning Poverty - financial inclusion-related variables are poor and considerable, demonstrating extremely good potential to lower the poverty degrees in LATIM international locations (Eduardo Polloni Silva et al., 1st June 2021). consistent with Lee (2009), the perceived risk has a substantial adverse effect on an individual's mindset in the direction of the usage of particular technological products or services. With the improvement of financial services, development of facts technologies, and evolution of financial sectors, FinTech has emerged as a brand new possibility within the financial industry (Cham Tat Huei, Low Suet Cheng, et al., 2018). In addition, Dakshata Nair et al. 2021 recommended from their research findings for Strategies to Overcome COVID-19 Challenges - Fintech responds quickly to economic challenges and develops creative consumer goods and services. Expertise concerning financial services is one of the most influential forces to sell inclusive finance. It additionally has a good-sized contribution to developing economic conversation abilities for rural and decrease-earnings nation-state human beings (Morshadul Hasan et al., 2018).

Due to the rapid development of IT technology and the increase in the need for convenient payment methods, security and safety also play a dominant role in the digital world. Fintech has enabled mobile payment through a single payment service (Jungho Kang, Korea. 2018). Exploratory case study approach (Yin 2009), as the focus is on realizing the present dynamics interviews, the study aimed to identify critical success factors for the execution of FinTech projects (Dakshitha N. Jinasena* et al., 2020, England). Though most of the research studies on fintech impact revealed the facts, only a few have been found on customers' acceptance of Fintech. (Lan-TN Le et al., 2021 UK.) found that designing an effective diversification strategy.

In the finance Industry, the transformation phase was clearly studied by (Rainer Alt et al., 2018) and found in their study that "step builds at the evolution and convergence of a couple of technology (e.g., mobile gadgets, wi-fi networks, net technology), then again, neither customer-orientation nor innovation or entrepreneurial spirit featured the same presence and aggregate before the FinTech movement. The USD maintained its specific role within the international economic system and the so-called exorbitant privilege it enjoys. another observe found that this observe stimulates more enormous hobby within the novel application of a CAS framework in embracing the multi-faceted nature of generation [109] and creates new avenues for the development of the IS subject (Priyadarshini Muthukannan et al., 2020).

The fintech market reaches adulthood, and plenty of hurdles to overcome to protect traders without snuffing out innovation. it is also probably that Fintech will continue to evolve, and new innovations will replace or refine current technologies found out (Helen Bollaert et al., 2021). associated with the era element, a examine determined that 5 technical factors protected data-orientated techniques, facility and equipment improvement, application designs, carrier models placement, and protection and privacy protections (Keke Gai, Meikang Qiu a b, Xiaotong Suna., 2018). although, Smartphones plays very crucial role in fintech boom in current scenario.

as a result, a observe famous that modularity allows the easy performing of systemically essential cellular fee, processing, clearing, and agreement, which might be aligned with public dreams and public services. within the mobile charge region, the transition towards modular settings appears to be adopted from the organizational structure to a pre-existing provider and product architecture (Nofie Iman., 2018, Indonesia). additional to a smartphone for the clients however for the business firms, enterprise models also are equally critical for the corporations. A take a look at famous that 4 critical enterprise models to fee service, lending community, and financial markets middleman archetypes proposed with the aid of Eickhoff et al. (2017). The perception that the enterprise model of FinTech isn't equivalent to its principal hobby, as taken into consideration in a few earlier works (e.g., Lee and Shin, 2018; Liu et al., 2020). As vast modifications in FinTech enterprise fashions are predicted to preserve, further studies is wanted into the steadily evolving attributes of FinTech business models (Laivi Laidroo et al., 2021).

another enormous aspect is the regulatory demanding situations and answers confronted by using fintech corporations. A look at reveals that developing a accurate method in regulating FinTechs. this could allow FinTechs and Banks to define duties more really; consequently, whilst they try to collaborate, as opposed to discussing terms and conditions for months, both parties can focus on how they are able to create cost for clients in a fast and efficient way (Kazim Degerli., 2019, Turkey). one of the vital variables to study the consumer's willingness is safety and safety to make digital payments and lendings. The virtual forensics thing of the research located a few critical key components (Bruce Nikkel., 2021):

In addition, the Financial literacy of the people plays a dominant role in using fintech applications. The research study on "How does financial literacy impact inclusive finance?" reveals three procedures to getting monetary access: banking, microfinance, and FinTech (mobile banking). Some variables confirmed minor consequences because their lack of know-how about economic activities became taken into consideration as the obstacle to preventing monetary access development (Morshadul Hasan et al., 2021).

Under the impact of the pandemic, many elements at exclusive ranges have lowered FSPs' expectancy of financing SMEs. among these factors, insufficient economic assets and informatization competencies are every day demanding situations for a few FSPs, and the absence of coordination with focal firms is a venture for almost half of them. Concerning the elements of forms of financial carrier carriers support small- and medium establishments, take a look at performed and screen that most FSPs ask for the assist to get admission to public records from public administrations at the group level, allowing online due diligence using regulators and increasing liquidity. Credit-improved FSPs are in extra want of capital, growing liquidity, and aid from peer FSPs. But, they've comparative advantages in informatization functionality and collaboration with focal firms (Hua Song, Yudong Yang and Zheng Tao*. 2020, China). The customer-oriented service offering by fintech start-ups plays a crucial role in the growth of Fintech at the time covid pandemic situation (Henner Gimpe et al., 2018) study found that it helps evaluate and realize FinTech start-up assistance subscriptions.

Figure 2: Proposed model for customers willing towards Fintech firms

Source: Author's own; a result of data collection tabulation.

Note: PEOU: Perceived ease of use; PU: Perceived usefulness; ST: Security and trust; UA: User Attitude; UB: User Behaviour; AU: Actual Usage

3. Aim of the Study

The research study aims to find out the fintech usage by the consumers at the time of the pandemic evidence-based survey in India. India was overtaking China and became the second-largest Fintech Digital ecosystem hub in Asia. Though the financial literacy rate in India is too low, perhaps the usage of fintech applications is increasing rapidly due to the impact of the covid pandemic on the whole economy. The study tries to determine what factors make the customers inculcate fintech apps for digital transactions for day-to-day transactions.

1. The study aims to know the factors influencing customer's willingness towards fintech products and services.
2. To know the customer's behavior or mindset towards various fintech applications for usage.
3. To know whether demographic factors influence the fintech usage by the users.

3.1 Research Objectives and Hypotheses:

This research paper is considering as per the research agenda. The study aims to know the factors influencing the customers' willingness and acceptance towards using the fintech applications in a COVID pandemic situation. To acquire the goals of gauging the popularity, consciousness, and attitude of Indian customers toward FinTech applications.

H₁: PEOU is a significant predictor of the user attitude towards the adoption of fintech firms

H₂: PU is a substantial predictor of user attitude towards the adoption of fintech firms

H₃: ST is a significant predictor of user attitude towards the adoption of fintech firms

H₄: UA is a substantial predictor of user behavior intention towards the adoption of fintech firms

H₅: UB is a significant predictor of user acceptance of adoption of fintech firms

4. Research Methodology

4.1 Instrument:

The data series is collected through an online google form questionnaire. The developed survey instrument contained information on constructs and their constituents. The designed questionnaire had two components. Part A consists of the demographic traits of the respondents, such as gender, age, educational qualification, and employment status. Part B measures the model variables, which constitute five constructs and one dependent variable. The instrument finally had fourteen items measuring the input factors. The item measured the user acceptance to adopt the fintech firm's product and services.

In order to assess the drivers influencing the behavior of consumers towards fintech apps, it is necessary to identify the reasons for using them in pre and post-pandemic situations. While framing the questions, researchers have added the core factors that reveal the facts for using financial technology applications. Those factors or variables include perceived ease of use, security & trust, perceived usefulness, user attitude, user behavior, and actual usage of fintech firm's products and services. Part- B consists of sixteen questions drafted to adopt fintech applications and circulated to the age groups that fall under the category of above age 16 to 60 online. Thus, in the final questionnaire, all factors except the demographical profile and customer willingness towards Fintech services usage frequency were assessed on a five-point Likert scale (5 = strongly agree and 1 = strongly disagree). The respondents were requested to give their frequency of usage of fintech applications on day-to-day transactions. Due to the covid pandemic, the data was collected through Google forms during Feb – April 2021 and collected sample 92 respondents from Bengaluru, Karnataka. Then data were coded by using the SPSS software package.

5. Results

5.1 Demographic Characteristics: The survey has been conducted to 92 respondents, Out of 92 respondents 62 respondents (69%) were in the age group less than 30 years. Approximately 31% of the respondents were between 30 to above 50 age group. A majority, 60% of the respondents, were male, and 40% were female. The preferred FinTech service for the respondents was Google pay and Phone Pe (80.4%), followed by other applications.

Figure 3: FinTech application usage by the respondents for their day-day transactions.

It is observed that few respondents (non-adoptors) refused to use FinTech products and services due to various factors such as safety and security issues(55%), lack of trust(11%), not being aware much of how to use FinTech applications. Figure 4 depicts the reason for non-adopting FinTech.

Figure 4 reasons for non-adopting FinTech services.

The study employed a multi-regression model to investigate the predictive relationship between the five exogenous variables. They are PEOU(Perceived ease of use), PU (Perceived usefulness), ST (Security and Trust), UA (User attitude), and UB (User behavior). The endogenous variable was User Actual usage. The hypothesized model includes five exogenous variables and one endogenous variable. PEOU, PU, ST, UA, and UB are measure using sixteen sub-items for each variable. Two items measure the user's actual usage of FinTech services. A regression model is used to validate the process.

5.2 Reliability Test: Reliability is the ability of the scale to produce consistent results. The study employed Cronbach's alpha to examine internal consistency between items of the construct. Cronbach's alpha of all the constructs is above the threshold limit of 0.6 (Hair et al., 1988), as seen in Table 1, thus supporting the reliability.

Table 1 Reliability

Construct	No. of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Perceived ease of use (PEOU)	3	0.83895
Perceived Usefulness (PU)	3	0.63635
Security and Trust (ST)	3	0.80945
User Attitude (UA)	3	0.65972
User Behaviour (UB)	2	0.71722
User Acceptance (UA)	2	0.8170
Total	16	0.87595*

Source: Author's own; the result of data collection tabulation.

Note: * overall Cronbach's Alpha

Table 2: Mean, SD, and Alpha for the measured indicators

Construct	Measured Indicators	Mean	SD	Alpha
PEOU	Easy to learn	4.17	0.97	0.86403
	Easy to use	4.17	0.87	0.86602
	Easy to transact	4.35	0.79	0.86017
UA	FinTech applications allows better control over transactions	4.28	0.75	0.86986
	FinTech applications are more convenient to do financial transactions	3.91	1.13	0.86284
UB	Recommend the adoption of FinTech products & services	4.09	0.83	0.87172
	Speak favorably about FinTech products and services	3.88	1.1	0.88093
S&T	Safe to complete the transaction	4.28	0.69	0.86951
	Service is trustworthy	3.59	1.22	0.87086
	FinTech apps has good reputation	4.09	0.75	0.86327
UA	I am more inclined to FinTech apps	3.96	1.15	0.87436
	FinTech app is wise to use during covid-19	4.43	0.86	0.86363
	It makes sense to use FinTech apps instead of cash transaction	3.91	0.83	0.86572
PU	Useful in daily life	4.22	0.98	0.87109
	Useful to do financial transaction quickly	3.04	1.51	0.8796
	Increase productivity	3.65	0.99	0.86587

Source: Author's own; the result of data collection tabulated

Table 3 shows that all the measured indicators have alpha values above the threshold point of 0.5. All are significant at a 0.5 percent level of significance. Thus, the above result supports reliability, and the model retains all the indicators for the study's relevance.

5.3 Regression model fit for perceived ease of use (PEOU) and user attitude (UA)

The perceived ease of use (PEOU) is the dependent variable that significantly positively affects user mindset. According to Table 9., the R square value of .502 indicates that PEOU explains 51% of user mindset (UM).

Table 3: Showing the regression analysis result of Perceived Ease of Use and User Mindset (Perceived Ease of Use is a Dependent variable)

Model Fit	Co-efficient	t-value	Significant (p-value)
Intercept	.800	9.520	.000
Ease of Use	.893	2.556	.012

Hence,

R = 0.708

R Square = 0.502

F Change Value = 90.635

Durban Watson value = 1.800.

Thus, the model in Table no. 9 illustrates that the user mindset strongly determines the fintech application users by the positive perceived ease of use of technology. The F value of 90.635 is significant, with a p-value is less than 0.05 (5%).

Hence, H₁ is confirmed by the outcome of the results.

Regression Model Analysis for Perceived Ease of Use (PEoU) and User Mindset

User mindset is the independent variable in this model, and perceived ease of use is the dependent variable. The impact of the independent variable on user mindset to access the fintech applications of the user is shown in Table 10 below.

Table 4: Showing the result of perceived ease of use and User mindset (dependent variable is perceived ease of use)

Model Fit	Coefficient	t-value	Significance (p-value)
Intercept	1.00	5.108	0.00
PeoU	0.15	2.210	0.037

Thus,

R = 0.474

R Square = 0.225

F Change Value = 26.090

Durban Watson value = 2.009.

As per the results shown in the above table, Perceived Ease of use may not desirably explain the positive behavior of the fintech users. T square value is at 5% effect on the mindset of the users. The model results found that the F-value of 26.090, t-value is 2.210 for PEOU was found to be significant with a p-value less than 0.05 (5%).

Regression Model Analysis for Security and Trust (S&T) and User Mindset (UM)

To know the degree of influence among the key variables between security & trust, on the other hand, user mindset using the regression model, User mindset is the independent variable, and security and trust are the dependent variables. The impact of the independent variable on user mindset to use the fintech applications of the user has a relative effect. The results show in the given below Table 11.

Table 5: Showing the result of Security and Trust and User mindset (dependent variable is Security and Trust (S&T))

Model Fit	Coefficient	t-value	Significance (p-value)
Intercept	1.000	6.729	0.000
S&T	0.10	2.675	0.10

Thus,
R = 0.579
R Square = 0.335
F Change Value = 45.283
Durban Watson value = 2.371.

From the above results, the regression model examines that user's mindset and security and trust in their behavioral perception towards fintech applications is quite valid. Users' mindset towards fintech apps dependent on trust and safety for usage is highly acceptable. Regression model results found that the F-value of 45.283, t-value is 2.675 for S&T, was significant with a p-value less than 0.10 (1%).

A Regression Model Analysis for User Mindset (UM) as a dependent variable and all others are PEOU, PU, S&T & UB (Independent variables)

This model examines the acceptance or willingness of fintech applications used by the respondents grounded on the independent factors such as perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, security and trust, and user behavior relationship with User mindset (dependent variable) in the regression model; it is highly correlated. The model summary is shown in Table 12.

Table 6: Showing the results of for User Mindset (UM) as a dependent variable and all other drivers are PEOU, PU, S&T & UB (Independent variables)

Model Fit	Coefficient	t-value	Significance (p-value)
Intercept		1.884	0.063
PEoU	.420	5.136	0.000
PU	-.008	-.095	0.925
S&T	.296	4.182	0.000
UB	.288	3.106	0.003

Hence,

R = 0.811

R Square = 0.658

F Change Value = 41.798

Durban Watson value = 2.106

From the above Table 11, The regression model examines that users' mindset as a dependent variable and others are independent variables such PEOU, PU, security, and trust on their behavioral perception towards fintech applications are significantly influencing by the user's intentions and mindset. The R square value of 0.658 indicates a 65% effect on the actual willingness/acceptance by the user's mindset and purpose of using fintech apps at the time of the covid pandemic situation. The F change value of 41.79%, t value of 5.136, 4.182, 3.106 except -.095.

After confirming the measurement model, the regression model fit was developed to test the stated hypotheses. The regression model was tested through SPSS (ver.25). The outcome shows an acceptable fit for the proposed model with F test = 47.79, R square = 65.8,

Attitude → PEOU, PU and S&T.

Table7. Hypothesis Results

Hypothesis	Construct (Hypothesis Path)	T value	Std. Co (β)	Significance (p) value	Result (S)
H1	EoU $\rightarrow$ UA	6.403	.559	0.000	Significant
H2	PU $\rightarrow$ UA	3.802	.372	0.000	Significant
H3	S&T $\rightarrow$ UA	5.103	.474	0.000	Significant
H4	S&T $\rightarrow$ UB	4.784	.450	0.000	Significant
H5	UA $\rightarrow$ UB	5.066	.471	0.000	Significant
H6	UA $\rightarrow$ AU	6.697	.577	0.000	Significant
H7	UB $\rightarrow$ AU	3.184	.318	0.002	Significant
H8	S&T $\rightarrow$ AU	5.438	.497	0.000	Significant

Source: Author's own; result of data collection tabulation.

Note: $p < 0.05$. S = Significant; EoU: Ease of Use; PU: Perceived usefulness; S&T: Security and Trust; UA: User attitude; UB: User Behaviour, Std. Co β = standard Coefficient Beta.

6. Structured Equation Modelling

Structural equation modeling (SEM), also referred to as analysis of covariance structures and causal modeling, is a family of statistical techniques which includes confirmatory factor analysis (CFA), structural regression, path, growth, multiple-groups, and multi-trait multi-method (MTMM) models. Proposed SEM model is presented below in path diagram form following established conventions.

Figure 5 Structural Model Results

Assessment of normality (Group number 1)

Variable	min	max	skew	c.r.	kurtosis	c.r.
AU1	3.000	5.000	-0.506	-1.982	-1.041	-2.037
AU2	1.000	5.000	-1.037	-4.061	.268	.524
UB2	1.000	5.000	-1.215	-4.757	1.190	2.331
UB1	1.000	5.000	-1.077	-4.219	2.161	4.231
UA3	1.000	5.000	-.751	-2.940	1.394	2.730
UA2	3.000	5.000	-.142	-.556	-1.198	-2.345
UA1	1.000	5.000	-1.056	-4.134	.521	1.020
ST3	1.000	5.000	-1.807	-7.078	3.787	7.415
ST2	1.000	5.000	-.500	-1.957	-.695	-1.361
ST1	3.000	5.000	-.421	-1.650	-.835	-1.635
PU3	1.000	5.000	-.222	-.870	-.400	-.784
PU2	1.000	5.000	-.036	-.139	-1.484	-2.906
PU1	1.000	5.000	-1.287	-5.040	1.247	2.442
PEOU3	2.000	5.000	-.966	-3.785	.115	.225
PEOU2	2.000	5.000	-.543	-2.126	-.964	-1.887
PEOU1	1.000	5.000	-1.084	-4.247	.830	1.625
Multivariate					19.514	3.899

Computation of degrees of freedom (Default model)

Number of distinct sample moments:	152
Number of distinct parameters to be estimated:	48
Degrees of freedom (152 - 48):	104

Results:

Minimum was achieved

Chi-square = 653.719

Degrees of freedom = 104

Probability level = .000

Maximization likelihood Estimation Method Regression Weights:

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
UB	<---	AU	.564	.143	3.944	***	
UA	<---	AU	.684	.194	3.535	***	
ST	<---	AU	.523	.120	4.378	***	
PU	<---	AU	.806	.174	4.644	***	
PEOU	<---	AU	1.085	.185	5.879	***	
PEOU1	<---	PEOU	1.000				
PEOU2	<---	PEOU	.848	.119	7.151	***	
PEOU3	<---	PEOU	.964	.103	9.328	***	
PU1	<---	PU	1.000				
PU2	<---	PU	.959	.320	2.998	.003	
PU3	<---	PU	.900	.223	4.041	***	
ST1	<---	ST	1.000				
ST2	<---	ST	1.553	.430	3.610	***	
ST3	<---	ST	1.749	.359	4.867	***	
UA1	<---	UA	1.000				
UA2	<---	UA	.981	.277	3.543	***	
UA3	<---	UA	1.097	.309	3.554	***	
UB1	<---	UB	1.000				
UB2	<---	UB	.961	.355	2.708	.007	
AU2	<---	AU	1.000				
AU1	<---	AU	.650	.133	4.871	***	

Standardized Regression Weights:

			Estimate
UB	<---	AU	1.000
UA	<---	AU	1.000
ST	<---	AU	1.000
PU	<---	AU	1.000
PEOU	<---	AU	1.000
PEOU1	<---	PEOU	.767
PEOU2	<---	PEOU	.722
PEOU3	<---	PEOU	.904
PU1	<---	PU	.561
PU2	<---	PU	.350
PU3	<---	PU	.502
ST1	<---	ST	.522
ST2	<---	ST	.457
ST3	<---	ST	.731
UA1	<---	UA	.408
UA2	<---	UA	.611
UA3	<---	UA	.616
UB1	<---	UB	.462
UB2	<---	UB	.337
AU2	<---	AU	.607
AU1	<---	AU	.596

Direct Effects

	AU	UB	UA	ST	PU	PEOU
UB	.564	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
UA	.684	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
ST	.523	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
PU	.806	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
PEOU	1.085	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
AU1	.650	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
AU2	1.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
UB2	.000	.961	.000	.000	.000	.000
UB1	.000	1.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
UA3	.000	.000	1.097	.000	.000	.000
UA2	.000	.000	.981	.000	.000	.000
UA1	.000	.000	1.000	.000	.000	.000
ST3	.000	.000	.000	1.749	.000	.000
ST2	.000	.000	.000	1.553	.000	.000
ST1	.000	.000	.000	1.000	.000	.000
PU3	.000	.000	.000	.000	.900	.000
PU2	.000	.000	.000	.000	.959	.000
PU1	.000	.000	.000	.000	1.000	.000
PEOU3	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.964
PEOU2	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.848
PEOU1	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	1.000

The empirical part of the current study supported the proposed hypotheses of the conceptual model. For example, the results of the confirmatory factor analyses supported the goodness-of-fit, reliability, and validity of second-order factors: fintech applications relationship with the end users at the COVID pandemic situations. The whole measurement model was also able to adequately fit the observed data, and all factors matched the criteria pertaining to reliability and validity.

7. Conclusion and Research Implications

In the background of the distraction caused by COVID-19 pandemic that has positively impacted and increase in usage of fintech products and services among the people who are living in India. The current have a look at observes the interplay of critical elements that have an effect on customers of virtual fintech programs and offerings. From the theoretical angle, the look at adds to the constructs' know-how and lends explanation to the linkages between them, as set up within the various fiction. With the aid of analyzing clients' mindset and behavior in the utilization of fintech apps are rapidly developing inside the marketplace.

Man or woman behavior in mild of the exchange caused via the pandemic. The take a look at establishes its theoretical usefulness through pointing in the direction of the relevance of addressing the precise elements (PEoU, S&T, PU, UM and UB) that practice power on customers' behaviour inside the present day scenario. Further, an exploration into the feasible moderating position of the 'consumer mindset' sample, brought on because of the pandemic, provides cost to the existing frame of studies.

At the practical front, the effects set up a strong impact of those critical factors, including PEoU, S&T and PU in influencing the patron's willingness and attractiveness towards financial technology products and services during the COVID-19 pandemic in destiny. To manipulate this nexus fintech carriers want to offer continuous attention to those aspects that enhance consumer satisfaction and user enjoyment. Clients also expressed that why they won't advocate to use for others due network error, banks cannot system bills made through fintech apps and many others.

A few beneficial implications evolving from the take a look at findings are cited.

Firstly, the study recommended that fintech providers commit interest on developing a sizeable purchaser phase to draw and retain the customers who're regularly do enterprise transactions who engaged with the companies from micro to macro commercial enterprise operations and its services. To achieve, the extra focus should be laid through fintech carriers to show regular information updates to their cash transactions fast. So, that it encourages people to stay up for do transactions actively. It is also seen that providers employ social networking sites, commercials, coupons imparting, bargain, etc., in apps. That encourages them to broaden a sizable user community.

8. Limitations of the Study and Scope for Further Research

Scholars can address the limitations of the present research in the future. The first constraint pertains to the sample that largely founds young respondents. A more diversified model including people from higher age groups may present a different perspective to the consumption of usage of fintech apps and services and yield a significant population effect. Another aspect that needs attention is the financial literacy impact on the usage of fintech apps is missing in the present work. The sample size of the respondents are less that can be considered as another limitations of the study.

The future researchers would be able to provide a more detailed and general valuation of these constructs, and also, they can add other core factors to know the variables supporting the rapid growth of Fintech in the Indian economy furthering user satisfaction with products and services. Lastly, there always remains a scope further to improve the psychometric and analytical properties of the measures and make future studies more comprehensive by including other relevant constructs in the conceptual research framework.

Authors Contribution

Mr. Vijay Kumar V M conceived the idea and developed qualitative and quantitative design to undertake the empirical study and extracted research papers with high repute, filtered those words based on keywords, and generated concepts and codes relevant to the study design. Dr. Senthil Kumar J P verified the analytical methods and supervised the study. The numerical computations, structural equation modelling and its results were done by Dr. Ravi Aluvala.

Declaration of Conflicting Interests

The authors certify that they have no affiliations with or involvement in any organization or entity with any financial interest, or non-financial interest in the subject matter, or materials discussed in this manuscript.

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